

eDNAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Recommendations for implementing DNA-based methods into the Water Framework Directive and Marine Strategy Framework Directive

Deliverable 4.2

Work Package 4

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Abbreviations, terms and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym/ Term	Definition
BQE	Biological Quality Element (WFD)
CIS	Common Implementation Strategy - an informal cooperation under the Water Framework Directive to support its implementation. The strategy gathers representatives from Member States, EEA/EFTA countries and all relevant stakeholders. The CIS also serves as a platform for the exchange of experience and develops guidance documents and policy papers
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA Barcode	A short DNA sequence from a standardised region of the genome that is used to identify species by comparison with reference sequences in a database
DwC	Darwin Core (metadata standard developed and maintained by TDWG)
EC	European Commission
ECOSTAT	EU WFD ecological status working group.
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EDTIO	Core infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean
EEA	European Environment Agency
EMODnet	European Marine Observation Data network
EQR	Ecological Quality Ratio (WFD)
ESC	Ecological Status Class (WFD)
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FAIRe	FAIR eDNA project
GES	Good Environmental Status (MSFD)
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
HELCOM	Intergovernmental commission protecting the Baltic Sea marine environment
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
Metabarcoding	Method to identify multiple species in a mixed sample using DNA barcodes and high-throughput sequencing
Metagenomics	Metagenomics is the analysis of all DNA in an environmental sample using direct shotgun sequencing to study the genetic composition of entire biological communities
MiXs	Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MS	European Union Member State
NIS	Non-indigenous species
OSPAR	International convention for the protection of the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards, non-profit organisation developing standards, like DwC
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WISE / WISE-marine	European databases that contain WFD/MSFD reporting data

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0 Summary

The eDNAquaPlan project develops a vision for a future digital ecosystem for DNA-based biodiversity data. In this report we provide input on specific requirements for integrating such a system with two key aquatic European directives - the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Both directives are formal regulatory frameworks with strict requirements for ecological assessment targets and reporting. Therefore they require biomonitoring data that are transparent, comparable and reproducible across Member States (MSs) and over time. **A central requirement shared by both directives is the use of valid and stable taxonomic references.** Taxonomy used in assessments must be clearly defined, fixed for reporting cycles, and version-controlled rather than continuously changing, ensuring traceability and comparability of results over time. This is particularly relevant for eDNA-based monitoring systems, which rely on reference databases that are often dynamic. Ensuring transparent versioning and documentation of reference databases is therefore a key prerequisite for the use of DNA-based methods in regulatory monitoring. Our review identified that the integration of DNA-based monitoring into WFD and MSFD implementation must also address data interoperability and reporting compatibility. DNA-derived biodiversity data are typically described using internationally recognised metadata standards such as MIxS for sequence and sample metadata and Darwin Core (DwC) for biodiversity observations. However, policy reporting systems such as WISE and WISE-Marine currently use dedicated schemas and vocabularies developed for morphology-based monitoring. **To ensure compatibility between molecular data and policy reporting, sustained semantic mappings between DwC/MIxS metadata terms and WFD/MSFD reporting vocabularies are required.** Such mappings would allow DNA-based biodiversity datasets to be translated into policy-relevant reporting formats while maintaining traceability to the underlying sequence data and analytical workflows. Furthermore - and in line with eDNAquaPlan's general recommendations, we highlight the need that **DNA-based monitoring data are archived in international sequence repositories**, particularly those of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). Depositing sequence data together with relevant metadata ensures long-term accessibility, persistent identifiers and the possibility of re-analysis. Linking these repositories with biodiversity data infrastructures and policy reporting systems will significantly improve the findability, accessibility and comparability of monitoring data across MSs. Finally, the integration of DNA-based methods into WFD and MSFD monitoring requires the **development of harmonised methodological guidance, standards and intercalibration procedures between traditional and molecular monitoring approaches** to build a bridge between data continuity and innovation. While DNA-based methods already provide valuable complementary information for biodiversity assessments, some indicators required under current directives - such as abundance, biomass or age structure - cannot yet be fully derived from DNA data alone. In the short term, DNA-based approaches will therefore complement existing monitoring systems and help fill gaps in spatial and temporal coverage. Over time, the establishment of interoperable data infrastructures, harmonised standards and transparent data reporting will empower DNA-based biodiversity monitoring to become an integral component of European environmental monitoring frameworks. Further, these will **maximise the reuse of biodiversity data generated through public monitoring programmes for all sectors, feeding more FAIR biodiversity data to European and global data infrastructures**, including EMODnet (the European Marine Observation and Data Network) and enriching the biodiversity component of the EDITO infrastructure, underpinning the European Digital Twin Ocean. The principles discussed in this report are therefore also relevant for broader biodiversity monitoring frameworks, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and international agreements such as the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

1 Introduction

The goal of eDNAqua-Plan is to develop a concept for a digital ecosystem for DNA-based biodiversity assessments from sampling across all laboratory handling steps to sequencing, bioinformatic data processing and publication. The envisioned workflow is intended to cover different source materials, i.e. environmental DNA (eDNA) or DNA obtained from organismal bulk samples, and a broad range of methods, e.g. single-species-based assessments, DNA metabarcoding, and metagenomics. For reasons of inclusivity, we will use the term “DNA-based” or “(e)DNA-based” methods.

1.1 The current and future digital (e)DNA ecosystem

The current digital eDNA data landscape encompasses any DNA biodiversity data, i.e. not only eDNA data but also specimen-based bulk-sample data. As assessed by WP2 and 3 the current digital landscape is fragmented consisting of numerous, often disconnected sequence repositories and reference sequence databases. While the necessary infrastructures for DNA-based data generation, storage and processing exists, significant challenges hinder its effectiveness. Data and metadata are frequently siloed, with inconsistent use of existing metadata standards and individual “in-house” or sector-specific formats leading to a lack of interoperability. This results in data that is difficult to find, access, and reuse, undermining the FAIR principles. Furthermore, data creators face confusion about where and how to submit their data, and there is a lack of seamless pathways from local or national repositories to global ones like GBIF and OBIS.

The proposed eDNAqua-Plan future landscape aims to transform this fragmented system into a harmonised, federated network. The core vision pragmatically identified in eDNAqua-Plan’s Future Landscape is “federation, not centralization,” leveraging existing resources while ensuring they are interconnected through universally adopted, interoperable standards. Key components to achieve the vision of an inclusive future digital (e)DNA data ecosystem relies on, in chronology, developing eDNA-specific Data Management Plan (DMP) templates with specific recommendations on metadata requirements, simplifying sequence data submissions to repositories like the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), creating conversion tools to align different metadata formats, promote the use of existing formal metadata standards for data collection rather than own individual solutions and adopt web-standard metadata-sharing technologies. The future system will also feature a network of connected, searchable reference libraries, with richer provenance metadata for samples and standardised, machine-readable protocols. This will unlock immense potential: data will be more easily discoverable, reusable, and interoperable, enabling powerful applications like AI-driven digital twins for ecosystem monitoring. The ultimate chance lies in creating a sustainable, community-driven ecosystem where data is treated as a primary research output, leading to more robust and large scale scientific insights and effective policy-making for Europe’s aquatic biodiversity.

However, requirements for data collection and publication can differ substantially between research settings and policy uptake contexts. Consultations with stakeholders involved in policy-related biomonitoring or biodiversity monitoring within the use cases (Work Package 4, WP4), as well as recent literature (e.g., Kelly et al. 2019; Blancher et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2024), highlight this difference. In regulatory contexts, data must be legally compliant and comparable across space and time. Therefore, the set of permitted methods and analytical approaches is typically more narrowly defined/prescribed than in research settings.

In the context of eDNAqua-Plan, WP4 assessed key data requirements of two aquatic-focused policies in order to highlight specific requirements and derive recommendations for the use of (e)DNA methods. In line with the original proposal, this report focuses on aspects of the European Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC¹) and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC²).

The objective of Deliverable D4.2 is to derive recommendations for integrating a proposed future landscape of a digital eDNA ecosystem into the WFD and MSFD. These recommendations are based on: (i) use cases aligned with the respective directives³, (ii) input from selected stakeholders consulted

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02000L0060-20140101>

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02008L0056-20170607>

³ Especially the [GEANS project](#), the [JDS4](#) DNA dataset, the German [GeDNA project](#)

as part of these use cases, (iii) a WP5 stakeholder workshop, and (iv) formal requirements outlined in the relevant legal documents and national implementation procedures. This report therefore reviews key requirements of the WFD and MSFD with respect to data use and identifies aspects particularly relevant to these directives. The findings are intended to inform WP5 and support the development of the final roadmap. Further input is required for a holistic picture of the WFD and MSFD recommendations.

1.2 Policy requirements by the EU Water Framework Directive

The main objective of the WFD is to achieve an at least good ecological and chemical status for all EU water bodies by 2027 to ensure good qualitative and quantitative health. The ecological status of water bodies is categorised into 5 ecological status classes (ESCs, high, good, moderate, poor, bad) and assessed separately per surface water body category (rivers, lakes, transitional and coastal waters) and their different types (see **Table 1**). Ecological quality status is inferred by separately analysing the biological quality elements (BQEs) of fish, benthic invertebrates, phytoplankton, and benthic flora (phytobenthos and macrophytes). The target value of an at least “good” ecological state is defined according to Annex V of the WFD as: “The values of the biological quality elements for the surface water body type show low levels of distortion resulting from human activity, but deviate only slightly from those normally associated with the surface water body type under undisturbed conditions.” In order to infer the ecological state across MSs these BQEs require sampling specimens in a standardised way (macrophytes are only surveyed, i.e. visually recorded and not sampled). Annex V of the WFD explicitly lists the use of specific international sampling and processing standards (**Table 1**). After sampling, organisms are identified based on their morphology and counted or other inferences (biomass inferences, age structure) are done where required. The resulting national taxa lists, including abundance or biomass data, are used for calculating national biological metrics (multi metric indices; observed values), which are subsequently compared to national reference conditions (reference value; implemented by the respective national agencies in charge of implementing the WFD⁴) for inferring the ecological status of a water body. This is done by calculating so-called ecological quality ratios (EQRs), which compare observed values against reference values. Reference conditions are water body type- and country-specific. The general procedures for assessing the ecological status in a WFD-compliant way are defined by the Common Implementation Strategy (CIS) working group ECOSTAT, which has also established the procedures to compare MS specific methods in an as much as possible unified way, termed the “Intercalibration Procedure”⁵. While the operationalisation and implementation of specific methodologies for water body monitoring are at the discretion of the MSs, reporting of the status of water bodies follows a predefined procedure. After reporting, the final information is available in WISE⁶, an EU database hosted by the European Environment Agency (EEA).

⁴ [https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/dce34c8d-6e3d-469a-a6f3-b733b829b691/Guidance%20No%2010%20-%20references%20conditions%20inland%20waters%20-%20REFCOND%20\(WG%202.3\).pdf](https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/dce34c8d-6e3d-469a-a6f3-b733b829b691/Guidance%20No%2010%20-%20references%20conditions%20inland%20waters%20-%20REFCOND%20(WG%202.3).pdf)

⁵ https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/61fcb5b-eb52-44fd-810a-63735d5e4775/IC_GUIDANCE_FINAL_16_Dec2010.pdf

⁶ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub/datahubitem-view/dc1b1cdf-5fa0-4535-8c89-10cc051e00db>

Table 1: Requirements of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) for compliant assessment of the ecological status of inland, transitional and coastal water bodies.

Requirement	Specifications
Five distinct status classes	The WFD requires all water bodies to be assigned a status based on Ecological Quality Ratios (EQRs).
Type specificity	Typology of the different surface water bodies (categories: rivers, lakes, transitional and coastal waters) per ecoregion, covering aspects of geology, size, altitude.
Reference conditions	Streams with no or very minor impact are used to define a reference condition, including their Biological Quality Elements (see below).
Biological Quality Elements (BQEs)	Organismal groups that are surveyed and compared against the reference conditions to infer deviations and identify pressures. BQEs are (depending on water body type): Phytoplankton, (other) Aquatic Flora, Benthic Invertebrate Fauna, Fish. Data on composition and abundance , but possibly also on biomass , age structure are required.
Boundary setting	Each water body type requires precisely defined status class boundaries, in particular for the High/Good and Good/Moderate class boundaries.
Standards	Annex V specifies that data must be generated according to listed methods standards, or that other national or international formal standards be used instead.

* Printed in italics-bold are aspects that DNA and eDNA methods cannot sufficiently cover at the given time.

1.2.1 Opportunities for DNA datasets in the context of the WFD

While the monitoring system of the WFD is well-developed and has considerably improved knowledge on European waters, it has also experienced several implementation challenges, which are summarised in the Fitness Check of EU water legislation published in 2019⁷. Key conclusions are that monitoring coverage remains incomplete and that some water bodies still have unknown ecological or chemical status. In addition, data flows and comparability between MSs are not yet fully harmonised. From the start of the implementation, interpretations of the normative definitions listed in Annex V varied between MSs, for example with respect to “abundance”. While “relative abundance” was considered by some MSs to fulfil abundance requirements, others used metrics based on “absolute abundance” (e.g. Pont et al. 2021). Consequently, currently more than 400 national assessment methods have been intercalibrated to align different ecological assessment metrics and ensure comparable ecological status boundaries across MSs (Birk et al. 2012). Another challenge identified for WFD monitoring relates to the substantial monitoring effort required, including the need for specialised expertise and analytical capacity. The fitness check also highlights that monitoring coverage remains incomplete in several areas and that further improvements in data collection and reporting are needed. In addition, the report emphasises the potential of innovative monitoring technologies, such as satellite observations, automated sensor technologies, drones and citizen science, to improve data collection, reduce monitoring costs and increase spatial and temporal coverage. DNA methods are also mentioned in this context (Carvalho et al. 2019) and possibilities to include these methods into the WFD context have been outlined by Hering et al. (2018) and validated as part of several national projects in MSs (e.g. Pérez-Burillo 2020; Macher et al. 2025). To discuss options and possible operational procedures among MSs, ECOSTAT has mandated an “eDNA task force” to explore innovative monitoring approaches that could complement existing methods.

⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/c6383764-8b90-4624-b91e-719a477ff870_en?filename=swd_2019_0439_en.pdf

1.2.2 Compliance of DNA-based data with WFD policy requirements

In view of the opportunities and the general fact that no formal barrier exists for the uptake of novel technologies like DNA-based tools into the WFD, it is important to focus on aspects where DNA-based data do not comply with the normative definitions of the WFD. These are in particular:

1. DNA-based data can often not provide exact abundance or biomass data (Elbrecht and Leese 2015),
2. DNA-based data currently provide neither information about size classes nor information about age structure (requirement for BQE fishes), and
3. there is still a lack of formal standards or explicit CIS guidance that would ensure sufficient robustness and reliability of the data.

1.3 Policy requirements by the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The MSFD constitutes a key European legislative instrument aimed at the protection, conservation, and restoration of European marine waters. The directive seeks to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) of marine waters to ensure that marine ecosystems remain healthy, clean, and productive while keeping an appropriate balance between ecological integrity and economic development. European MSs are required to develop national marine strategies, establish targeted programmes of measures, and implement robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks to evaluate whether their marine waters are in GES. These efforts need to be complemented by enhanced regional cooperation, recognising the transboundary nature of marine ecosystems. Reporting is done using templates provided by the European Union⁸ and all data are collected and made accessible through an open database⁹. Every six years, the proposed strategies are reviewed and updated. At this point, the third implementation cycle of MSFD is running (2024-2030).

In practice, each MS evaluates GES using 11 qualitative descriptors (**Table 2**). For each of these descriptors, primary and secondary criteria were added as amendments to the Directive in 2017. While the primary criteria should be used by MSs to ensure consistency across the EU, flexibility exists. MSs can focus on the predominant pressures and environmental impacts in their waters, and as such may consider that it is not appropriate to use one or more of the primary criteria. Each MS is responsible for setting up national thresholds that determine a baseline situation against which the targets listed in the national marine strategies can be compared, to evaluate whether progress has been made to achieve GES. At this point, guidelines on how to collect samples and obtain data to evaluate the thresholds for each of the descriptors largely rely on guiding documents from the Regional Sea Conventions (e.g., OSPAR, HELCOM). The Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme¹⁰ (CEMP) guidelines are used by MSs, but these guidelines merely list the methods that respective MSs are using rather than provide a standard for data collection and analyses.

While ambitions were high at the time of the MSFD adoption in 2008, as reflected in the 2020 deadline for achieving good environmental status for all marine waters, the reality has proven complex. Nevertheless, the MSFD remains legally binding and continues to operate through recurring six-year implementation cycles, requiring ongoing assessment, monitoring, and adaptation of measures. The directive applies to all European marine regions and subregions, including the Baltic Sea, North-East Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea and Black Sea. The evaluation of the first two MSFD cycles in 2025¹¹ concluded that GES has not been achieved, despite the fact that broad-scale marine data collection has become possible. Unfortunately, a lack of methodological standards and harmonised indicators as well as the FAIRness of the data leaves major knowledge gaps for many of the descriptors of the MSFD.

⁸ <https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/msfd/MSFD%202024>

⁹ <https://water.europa.eu/marine>

¹⁰ <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-monitoring-programmes/cemp/>

¹¹ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/document/659eea3a-8a00-410e-bc2f-f94baf210c9b_en

1.3.1 Opportunities for DNA-based monitoring datasets for MSFD

Marine monitoring under the MSFD is challenging in terms of time, infrastructure and personnel for sampling. Thus, the 2025 evaluation of the MSFD¹² identified a clear need for a better use of innovative and cost-effective monitoring and assessment methods, standards as well as harmonised and interoperable data management. DNA-based methods are one such key technology. Bulk DNA-based methods have proven to be cost effective and well suited for impact monitoring of marine macrobenthos (e.g., Aylagas et al. 2018, Van den Bulcke et al. 2024), while eDNA-based methods are already well-suited for monitoring marine fish communities (e.g., Sigsgaard et al. 2017, Miya et al. 2022, Cornelis et al. 2024). These studies have shown that morphology-based and DNA-based assessments are complementary methods where the former can provide quantitative information on biomass and density of species age and size, while the latter is more efficient in describing communities of marine species. The Interreg North Sea region funded project GEANS¹³ was the first project where a concerted effort by all neighboring North Sea countries was conducted to assess the need for a harmonised, cross-boundary DNA-based monitoring program. The project ran several pilot studies in collaboration with stakeholders. These pilot studies focused on soft-sediment macrobenthos communities (Descriptors 1 and 6), hard-substrate fauna, detection of NIS in harbors (Descriptor 2), and eDNA-based monitoring of fish (Descriptor 1 and 3). The project delivered a bulk DNA metabarcoding methodology for macrobenthos monitoring¹⁴, a curated North Sea region specific reference database (Christodoulou et al. 2025), and an interactive decision tree to help stakeholders choose the best approach for their monitoring question at hand¹⁵. This clearly helps to speed up the implementation process, since discussions on which protocols are best to use become less important and established national protocols can be used. By framing guidelines at a broader, more strategic level instead of at a detailed level, it is easier to adapt to rapid developments in the field, for instance with regard to improved quantification of species when using eDNA.

1.3.2 Compliance of DNA-based data with MSFD policy requirements

Similar to WFD, a CIS for the MSFD exists, which provides a forum for developing a common understanding of the different steps and milestones needed to implement the directive, to discuss its technical, scientific and socioeconomic implications, and to effectively address practical challenges. Focus within the task groups of CIS is on whether the various methods lead to similar thresholds. Although the MSFD allows the adoption of new methods, the systematic use of new data collection and monitoring techniques, such as eDNA analyses, is still limited, and the 2025 evaluation document considered this as a weakness in MSs' MSFD monitoring programmes. One reason for this is that although DNA-based monitoring can be used to measure several of the MSFD criteria (see **Table 2**), long-term datasets will be needed for some indicators (e.g., community changes over time) before they can be implemented in the MSFD framework. This restricts the current use of DNA-based methods, despite the promise of lower cost and faster turnaround time than morphology-based monitoring. In addition, the lack of methodological standards, while not strictly being a compliance criterion, limits data comparability. The flexibility of the MSFD allows each MS to conduct its monitoring in a way that is efficient (e.g., by integrating with ongoing monitoring efforts) and that fits the pressures and their impacts and the long-term knowledge of their regions (e.g., long-term monitoring data can be used to set the threshold baselines). However, the lack of explicitly demanded methodological standards hampers uniform data collection and comparison across MSs and consequently evaluation of GES at the regional or even subregional level is problematic. An important finding of the GEANS project, which is reflected in the recommendations of the MSFD review from 2025⁹, was that standardisation of procedures is essential. It needs to be achieved at the general level of how to collect, preserve and process samples, while slight changes to the laboratory protocol still allow robust macrobenthos measurements (Van den Bulcke et al. 2023).

¹² https://environment.ec.europa.eu/document/659eea3a-8a00-410e-bc2f-f94baf210c9b_en

¹³ <https://www.vliz.be/projects/geans/index.html>

¹⁴ <https://www.vliz.be/projects/geans/protocols/sbs.html>

¹⁵ <https://www.thinglink.com/card/1722208540866642406>

Table 2: List of 11 MSFD descriptors along with their primary and secondary criteria as provided in Commission Decision 2017/848 to evaluate GES. Suitability of DNA-based methods for each criterium is indicated in the last column, where “1” refers to DNA methods that have already been proven to work and are established, “2” referring to DNA methods under active development and “3” refers to DNA methods unlikely to provide information. Assignment of the three categories are based on literature, pilot results of the GEANS project and WP4 experiences.

1/ Criteria to assess predominant pressures and impacts			
Descriptor	Description	Criteria	Est.
2	Non-indigenous species do not adversely alter ecosystems	Primary: # NIS newly introduced since previous cycle	1
		Secondary: abundance and spatial distribution of established NIS	2
		Secondary: proportion of the species group or spatial extent of the broad habitat type which is adversely altered by NIS	2
3	Populations of commercial fish and shellfish species are healthy	Primary: fish mortality rate	3
		Primary: spawning stock biomass	3
		Primary: age and size distribution	3
5	Eutrophication is reduced	Primary: nutrient concentrations	3
		Primary: chl a concentrations or phytoplankton species composition and abundance	2
		Secondary: number, spatial extent and duration of HAB or phytoplankton species composition and abundance	2
		Secondary: photic limit of the water column	3
		Primary: concentration of dissolved oxygen	3
		Secondary: abundance of opportunistic macroalgae in benthic habitats	3
		Secondary: species composition and relative abundance or depth distribution of macrophyte communities of benthic habitats	3
6	Sea floor integrity ensures the proper functioning of ecosystems	Secondary: species composition and relative abundance of macrofaunal communities of benthic habitats	1
		Primary: physical loss of the seabed	3
		Primary: physical disturbance of the seabed	3
		Primary: spatial extent of each habitat type adversely affected (eg through changes in species composition and their relative abundance, absence of sensitive or fragile species or species providing a key function) by physical disturbance	1
7	Permanent alteration of hydrographical conditions does not adversely affect ecosystems	Secondary: spatial extent and distribution of permanent alteration of hydrographical conditions (e.g. changes in wave action, currents, salinity, temperature) to the seabed and water column, associated in particular with physical loss (1) of the natural seabed.	3
		Secondary: spatial extent of each benthic habitat type adversely affected (physical and hydrographical characteristics and associated biol. communities) due to permanent alteration of hydrogr. conditions.	1
8	Concentr. of contaminants give no pollution effects	Primary: concentrations of contaminants below threshold values	3
		Secondary: health of species and condition of the habitats	3
		Primary: significant acute pollution events	3
		Secondary: effect of significant acute pollution events on species composition and abundance of the species groups	1
9	Contaminants in seafood are at safe levels	Primary: concentration of contaminants in edible tissues	3
10	Marine litter does not cause harm	Primary: composition, amount and spatial distribution of litter on the coastline, water column and coastline	3
		Primary: composition, amount and spatial distribution of micro litter on the coastline, water column and sediment	3
		Secondary: amount of litter ingested by marine animals	3
		Secondary: number of ind. per species adversely affected due to litter	3
11	Introduction of energy (including underwater noise) does not adversely affect the ecosystem	Primary: anthropogenic impulsive sound sources	3
		Primary: anthropogenic continuous low frequency sound	3

2/ Criteria to assess essential features and characteristics and current environmental status of marine waters			
Descriptor	Description	Criteria	Est.
1	Biodiversity is maintained	Primary: mortality rate per species	3
	Target species groups: birds, fish, mammals, turtles	Primary: population abundance of the species (number of individuals or biomass)	2
		Primary for commercially exploited fish and cephalopods, secondary for other species: demographic features (age, body size)	3
		Primary: distribution range of species	1
		Primary: habitat for the species is in a condition that all life stages are supported	3
2	Pelagic habitats	Primary: the condition of the habitat type, including its biotic and abiotic structure and its functions (e.g. its typical species composition and their relative abundance, absence of particularly sensitive or fragile species or species providing a key function, size structure)	1*
1.6	Benthic habitats	Primary: loss of habitat due to anthropogenic pressures	3
		Primary: the extent of adverse effects from anthropogenic pressures on the condition of the habitat type, including alteration to its biotic and abiotic structure and its functions (e.g. its typical species composition and their relative abundance, absence of particularly sensitive or fragile species or species providing a key function, size structure of species)	1*
4	Food webs ensure long-term abundance and reproduction of species	Primary: the diversity (species composition and their relative abundance) of the trophic guild	1
		Primary: the balance of total abundance between the trophic guilds (total abundance (number of individuals or biomass in tonnes (t)) across all species within the trophic guild)	2
		Secondary: the size distribution of individuals across the trophic guild	3
		Secondary: productivity of the trophic guild	3

* not for size structure of species

2 General (e)DNA data considerations and recommendations for biodiversity monitoring

DNA-based methods offer a solution to fill existing gaps in biodiversity monitoring under the WFD and MSFD. They have been successfully applied across many organism groups targeted by these directives and can help overcome key challenges such as limited spatial and temporal coverage, lack of taxonomic expertise, inconsistent species identification, poor harmonisation of taxonomic lists, and in some instances high monitoring costs. For inferring aquatic communities, two main approaches are used: DNA metabarcoding, which amplifies and sequences specific DNA regions (barcodes) to identify species, and metagenomics, which directly sequences all DNA in a sample, reducing PCR-related biases and improving species quantification, particularly for complex samples like benthic sediments (Callens et al. 2025). To ensure high-quality and comparable (e)DNA data for WFD and MSFD assessments, consistent sampling, robust laboratory protocols, reliable reference databases (see eDNAquaPlan recommendation¹⁶), and transparent data processing are essential. However, formal standards are only under development and we witness a rapid divergence of approaches that jeopardises the unified application.

2.1 Method standards from sampling to taxonomic assignment

For the future implementation of DNA-based methods within the WFD ESC and MSFD GES assessments, standardised procedures are required for sampling and analysing all BQEs (WFD) and species groups (MSFD), as well as for laboratory processes including sequencing, bioinformatic processing of sequence data, taxonomic assignment, and the use and maintenance of reference databases. While standards or guidelines for most of the respective aspects already exist or are under development (**Table 3**) and largely fall outside the scope of eDNAqua-Plan, taxonomic assignment of sequence data remains a notable exception. The results of ESC and GES assessments can lead to legally-binding management actions of water bodies or sites with a status below “good”. Because of this legal obligation and the substantial financial resources required for implementing appropriate measures (e.g. restoration), the assessments done for ECS and GES - and the morphological identifications of taxa on which they are based - must be highly reliable and accurate. In this context, barcode reference databases used to assign sequences to taxa represent a critical interface in DNA metabarcoding workflows. However, taxonomic assignment is also one of the most debated and methodologically sensitive steps. Reference databases (or platforms used as such) are either largely uncurated but more comprehensive, or are curated but less comprehensive in their species coverage, resulting in a trade-off between broader coverage and higher taxonomic accuracy. Currently no standard exists for taxonomic annotation of sequences, for reporting the confidence or reliability of taxonomic assignments, or for handling ambiguous assignments. One reason is also the immense diversity of taxonomies leading to many synonyms (see Grenié et al. 2022 for an overview).

Recommendations:

- Use method standards for laboratory procedures or open and validated protocols
- Ensure transparency and reproducibility in taxonomic assignment until formal standards for the full DNA workflow are established by documenting key parameters (reference database used, assignment method applied, further parameter settings or thresholds)
- Use curated reference databases where available for the relevant policy or regional context (e.g. North Sea macrobenthos¹⁷)
- If no curated reference databases exist, document database content (e.g. number of species represented and sequences per species), the procedures used for its compilation and quality control, and provide a permanent, citable identifier (e.g. DOI) to ensure long-term accessibility.

¹⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/18849393>

¹⁷ <https://portal.boldsystems.org/recordset/DS-GEANS1>

Table 3: Exemplary overview of existing standards or best practice guidelines for the process of generating DNA data under the WFD or MSFD. This overview is not exhaustive but aims to highlight the aspects in the process chain of generating DNA-based biodiversity data that lack standardisation.

Analysis step	Standard / Guidelines (exemplary)
Sampling	ISO EN 17805 (eDNA capture and preservation from water samples); EN 17136 (invertebrate sampling with notes on DNA-conform storage), NP 25806 in development under ISO TC 147 SC5 WG13, many guidance documents for specific purposes, not standardised, e.g. [1 , 2 , 3 ; see 4 for an overview].
Laboratory processing	Formal standards currently developed such as NP 25807 by ISO TC 147 (water analysis), SC5, WG13.
Sequencing	ISO general library preparation and sequencing standard [5], specific recommendations for BQEs available in literature as recommendations.
Bioinformatic processing	No formal standard exists; guidelines from EU and other projects for diatom metabarcoding analysis, fish metabarcoding analysis [6].
Taxonomic assignment	No formal standards existing, but e.g. Technical Recommendation for diatom barcodes [7].
General reporting	Individual standards in non-European countries available [8]; recommendations in scientific literature [9].

2.2 Harmonised data description

For future biodiversity monitoring and assessment, DNA-based biodiversity datasets shall comprise more than sequence files alone: they should require structured metadata describing the full dataset as well as the workflow from sampling and laboratory processing to sequencing, bioinformatic analysis and taxonomic assignment. Considering the vast amount of sequence data and associated metadata being generated, scientific analyses will only be possible when machine-readable standard formats are used consistently. Current best practices for metadata descriptions, as summarised in eDNAquaPlan Deliverable D3.2¹⁸, use complementary international metadata standards, usually MIxS (Minimum Information about any Sequence) and DwC (Darwin Core). MIxS is a list of a standardised vocabulary developed by the Genomics Standards Consortium (GSC) used to describe sequence and environmental sample metadata within INSDC (International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration; i.e. ENA, NCBI, DDJB) repositories. DwC was developed by the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) to describe biodiversity observations and taxonomic occurrences in biodiversity data infrastructures such as GBIF¹⁹ and OBIS²⁰. Together, these standards allow DNA-derived biodiversity data to be documented in a consistent and reusable way across the research data ecosystem and support interoperability between sequence archives and biodiversity observation platforms.

By contrast, reporting under the WFD and MSFD currently follows policy-specific reporting frameworks developed primarily for morphology-based monitoring. Under the WFD, MSs report data through WISE using predefined XML schemas covering water bodies, monitoring programmes, methodologies and River Basin Management Plans. Reporting occurs at different spatial scales (water body, River Basin District and MS) and relies on structured schemas such as SWB (surface water bodies), GWB (groundwater bodies), Monitoring, Methodologies, and River Basin Management Plans and Programmes of Measures. These schemas include defined metadata elements describing the dataset,

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/18833237>

¹⁹ <https://www.gbif.org/>

²⁰ <https://obis.org/>

reporting organisation and licensing information to ensure comparability of reported data across MSs. Similarly, MSFD monitoring data are reported through Reportnet and WISE-Marine using standardised templates linked to Marine Reporting Units (MRUs) and the descriptors and criteria used to assess GES. Both policy frameworks therefore rely on controlled vocabularies, predefined reporting units and harmonised reporting structures. However, the current reporting schemas do not explicitly include key metadata elements required for DNA-based monitoring, such as sequence identifiers, barcode markers, laboratory protocols or bioinformatic workflows. In addition, the vocabulary is only partially overlapping with the generic DwC vocabulary.

The metadata standards used for DNA-based biodiversity data (DwC and MixS) and the reporting schemas used under the WFD and MSFD describe largely compatible core concepts such as sampling location, time, taxa and monitoring events. However, they differ in their structure and purpose: DwC and MixS are designed for biodiversity observations and sequence metadata, whereas WFD and MSFD reporting schemas are structured around water bodies, monitoring programmes and status assessments. If WFD and MSFD monitoring are to incorporate DNA-based methods in the future, interoperability between research metadata standards and policy reporting systems will be required. Rather than replacing existing reporting frameworks, a federated approach should be adopted in which MixS and DwC remain the primary standards for describing DNA-derived biodiversity datasets, while semantic mappings are developed between these standards and WFD/MSFD reporting vocabularies. Such mappings would allow DNA-based monitoring datasets to be translated into policy-relevant reporting formats while preserving traceability to the underlying sequence data, laboratory workflows and taxonomic assignments. This approach would enable the reuse of DNA-based datasets in policy assessments, improve interoperability across MSs and ensure consistency with existing EU reporting infrastructures.

Recommendations:

- Develop formal semantic mappings between DwC/MixS metadata terms and WFD/MSFD reporting vocabularies (e.g. WISE and Reportnet fields) to enable interoperable use of DNA-based monitoring data across MSs with these existing metadata standards.
- Integrating the assessment-oriented vocabulary of WFD and MSFD reporting into DwC terms should be considered to link to ESC and GES assessments with the biodiversity observation data.

2.3 Sequence data repositories

eDNAquaPlan recommends the use of repositories of the INSDC, and in particular ENA, for the long-term storage and dissemination of DNA-based biodiversity data. In line with the recommendations summarised in D3.2, DNA-based monitoring datasets should be deposited as demultiplexed sequence reads together with associated sample and project metadata (see Sec. 2.2). Once deposited in INSDC repositories, DNA-based datasets receive persistent identifiers and remain accessible to researchers, monitoring experts and policy agencies. This ensures that the underlying molecular data supporting ecological assessments remain available for verification, re-analysis or future methodological developments.

Recommendation:

- Use established international sequence repositories, particularly those of the INSDC and specifically ENA, for long-term storage and dissemination of DNA-based biodiversity data.
- Deposit monitoring datasets as demultiplexed sequence reads, together with associated sample and project metadata (see Section 2.2).
- Link repository datasets to policy reporting systems, such as WISE and WISE-Marine, so DNA-derived biodiversity observations support ESC and GES assessments while remaining traceable to the underlying molecular data.

3. Specific recommendations

3.1 Recommendations for WFD

Using DNA-based biodiversity data to assess ecological status classes (ESC) and identify pressures through indicator taxa is the long-term objective for integrating DNA-based methods into WFD monitoring. However, morphology-based and DNA-based identification methods will not produce identical taxa lists. Comparative studies consistently show that some taxa are detected by both approaches, while others are only detected by one method, for example due to juvenile life stages or morphologically cryptic species, primer bias or incomplete reference databases.

In addition, traditional monitoring generates specimen abundance data, whereas DNA-based approaches generate sequence abundance, which does not directly correspond to organism abundance. Some studies use relative read abundances as a proxy (e.g. diatoms: Tapolczai et al. 2024). As a conservative solution, many DNA-based assessments currently rely on presence–absence data. Studies have shown that ecological status classifications derived from such DNA-based taxa lists deviate only slightly from traditional assessments (e.g. benthic invertebrates: Elbrecht et al. 2017; Beentjes et al. 2018; Buchner et al. 2019). Recent large-scale comparative work has also demonstrated that intercalibration between morphological and DNA-based assessments is feasible when sampling covers all water body types and the full ecological status gradient with sufficient replication (Macher et al. 2025).

Consequently, the integration of DNA-based data into WFD assessments should focus on improving data comparability, ensuring interoperability of datasets across MSs and harmonising traditional and molecular monitoring approaches.

Recommendations and time frame (WP4 opinion):

Next 5 years:

- Support the work of ECOSTAT's task force in operationalising use cases of DNA-based methods for WFD implementation.
- Co-develop method guidance documents and reporting templates for DNA-based monitoring that align with CIS ECOSTAT requirements and WISE reporting formats.
- Advance the development of European (CEN) and international (ISO) standards for DNA-based monitoring methods applicable in WFD - but also ideally further aquatic assessments.
- Define criteria for reference sequence databases suitable for regulatory use, including quality control and provenance requirements - and ensure they are FAIR and regionally representative.
- Complete reference databases for assessment-relevant taxa groups, particularly zooplankton, phytoplankton and phytobenthos.
- Promote systematic data deposition in international sequence archives and biodiversity repositories to ensure accessibility and comparability of monitoring datasets across MSs.

Next 10 years:

- Perform formal intercalibration between morphological and DNA-based monitoring methods following CIS ECOSTAT procedures across all water body types and ecological status gradients.
- Identify metrics that remain robust without specimen abundance data and those requiring quantitative information.
- Develop end-to-end analytical workflow and reporting pipeline linking sequencing data to WFD-relevant indicators and assessment results.
- Provide training and capacity building for monitoring authorities and stakeholders to ensure the reliable implementation of DNA-based monitoring technologies.

3.2 Specific recommendations for MSFD

DNA-based monitoring methods are particularly well suited to address several MSFD descriptors, most notably descriptors 1, 2, 4 and 6. Descriptor 1 evaluates whether biodiversity is maintained compared to previous MSFD cycles. Target groups, such as fish, mammals and turtles and their distribution, can be effectively monitored with eDNA methods (Table 2). For Descriptor 6 (seabed integrity), DNA-based methods can characterise species composition, their relative abundance and the absence of fragile/sensitive species. Each MS has a list of key target species as well as ecological indicators (e.g., BEQI, relative Margaleff diversity) to assess the ecological state of the habitat. A healthy benthic habitat is characterized by high densities of long-living and slow-reproducing species and biogenic structure-forming species. For example, Belgian monitoring focuses on the detection and abundance of 17 macro/epibenthic species²¹. The current MSFD monitoring program is indirectly focusing on the occurrence of these key species and mainly focuses on assessing different human pressures (sand extraction, dredge disposal, fishery) and how it affects their occurrence and densities. The sampling techniques (grabs and trawls) currently in use are not optimal for monitoring some of these key species (e.g., those living in the seafloor's deeper layer), which could lead to an underestimation of their occurrence and abundance. Finally, DNA-based methods allow us to look at the diversity and relative abundance of several target groups of the food web from a single sample (Descriptor 4). While quantitative abundance or biomass estimates remain under development, they are progressing rapidly, particularly for metagenomics approaches (Callens et al. 2025). Integrating DNA-based methods could therefore enhance monitoring efficiency and complement morphology-based methods which remain essential for indicators that require absolute abundances or biomass, and the size distribution of key species.

Recommendations

Next 5 years:

- Integrate molecular expertise into the design of national MSFD monitoring programmes to identify where DNA-based approaches provide the greatest added value.
- Identify indicators and metrics suitable for DNA-based community composition data, and distinguish those that require quantitative abundance information.
- Develop standards and guidance documents (incl. DMPs) to ensure that DNA-based monitoring complies with MSFD criteria and thresholds (as well as other directives).
- Create DNA-based standards for MSFD-conform monitoring: all datasets should include metadata terms for the marine habitats and regions defined in MSFD, and at least a minimal set of basic metadata specifications linked to data collection, lab processing and bioinformatic analyses need to be provided so that information on how the species list was created can be retrieved at any point by any MS.
- Encourage MSs to integrate DNA-based monitoring into existing MSFD monitoring, particularly where current methods leave data gaps. Since evaluation of GES is done by comparing data against previous MSFD cycles, it is important to obtain DNA data as quickly as possible so that such data is available when the next reporting cycle starts.

Next 10 years:

- Design DNA-specific indicators that allow to evaluate the MSFD criteria and their thresholds
- Intercalibrate traditional and DNA-based assessments according to CIS recommendations.
- Develop a user-friendly end-to-end pipeline that delivers compliant and harmonised data and ensures data upload and archiving (from sample to taxa-lists to ecological indices)
- Train stakeholders involved in MSFD-based monitoring in the application of novel technologies.

²¹ https://odnature.naturalsciences.be/msfd_media/documents/D6-ANS-BE-BENTS-KSP-2024-Key-species-in-soft-sediments.pdf

4 Outlook

The development of a digital ecosystem for DNA-based biodiversity monitoring²² will continue independently of specific policy frameworks such as the WFD and MSFD. The principles discussed in this report are therefore also relevant for broader biodiversity monitoring frameworks, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030²³, the Nature Restoration Law²⁴, and international agreements such as the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework²⁵, all of which require scalable and harmonised biodiversity monitoring systems across ecosystems and jurisdictions.

Methodological standards, interoperable data infrastructures and harmonised reporting formats will be essential for enabling the systematic use of DNA-based data in environmental policy. In particular, ensuring that sequence data and associated metadata are archived in recognised repositories allows monitoring datasets to remain accessible and reusable beyond their original purpose.

Because DNA-based datasets can be archived and re-analysed, they offer significant potential beyond current WFD-centric ESC or MSFD-centric GES assessments. Sequence archives enable the exploration of previously unconsidered taxa and novel ecological indicators, including taxa that are not currently part of morphologically based monitoring programmes. This creates opportunities to develop new bioindicators, early warning systems for emerging environmental pressures, and AI-based analytical approaches that combine biodiversity data with other environmental datasets (e.g. Sanchez et al. 2025).

DNA-based monitoring also enables a more holistic perspective on ecosystem assessment, potentially capturing multiple components of aquatic food webs through metabarcoding or metagenomic approaches rather than focusing on a limited set of indicator groups. As highlighted by a WP4 use case on the Joint Danube Programme²⁶, the methods can support a transnational, from “source to sink” approach to biodiversity assessments²⁷. Further, these will maximise the reuse of biodiversity data generated through public monitoring programmes for all sectors, feeding more FAIR biodiversity data to European and global data infrastructures, including EMODnet (the European Marine Observation and Data Network) and enriching the biodiversity component of the EDITO infrastructure, underpinning the European Digital Twin Ocean.

To fully realise these opportunities, however, a comprehensive quality management framework must accompany the implementation of DNA-based monitoring approaches. Such a framework should cover all steps of the monitoring workflow, from sampling design and laboratory procedures to bioinformatic processing, data archiving and assessment reporting. It should include clear documentation standards, routine data deposition, and internal quality controls such as the use of spike-in controls or - ideally certified - reference materials. The continued development of such quality assurance systems will be essential to ensure that DNA-based monitoring data remain reliable, comparable and suitable for regulatory applications.

Restoring the health of Europe’s interconnected system of ocean, seas, coastal and inland waters is the ambition of the Horizon Europe Mission: Restore Our Ocean and Waters. With a specific objective and targets to protect and restore ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU’s Biodiversity Strategy, maximising the availability and usability of biodiversity data collected through public monitoring, in the context of the WFD and MSFD, would contribute to achieving these ambitions.

This report demonstrates that eDNA-based monitoring represents an innovative approach to biodiversity assessment, provided that common methodological standards, documentation requirements, and a robust quality management framework are in place.

5 References

²² <https://zenodo.org/records/17899468>

²³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0380>

²⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1991&qid=1722240349976>

²⁵ <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>

²⁶ <https://www.icpdr.org/tasks-topics/topics/water-quality/joint-danube-survey>

²⁷ <https://www.danubesurvey.org/jds4/publications/scientific-report.html>

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